

Preparation of Nutritious Fish Snacks by Using Tilapia Fish Muscle

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Abstract:

Now days many people need protein diet as it is beneficial for good health. Protein is an important part of a healthy diet. Tilapia is a wild exotic and invasive species that has spread across India and is now found in many of its waterways. Due to invasive nature, tilapia has affected the culture of indigenous fish species, so the government has established strict guidelines for tilapia farming. India's current tilapia production stands at approximately 70,000 metric tonnes with 30,000 metric tonnes from aquaculture and 40,000 metric tonnes from wild catches. This fish contains 26gm/100gm protein in its muscle. Nutritional values of this fish snack shows protein 18.20%/100gm in it as per results of food laboratory reports. Other than its dietary use an attempt is made to prepare fish snacks. This snack is prepared by using boiled fish muscle with different flours in 3:7 ratios. Nutritional values of this fish snack shows good content of protein and omega 3 fatty acids in it as per results of food laboratory. Shelf life of this snack is about 1 month without adding any type of preservatives. This product provides a great source of income and does not require any sophisticated equipment for preparation.

Keywords: Protein, Nutrients, Exotic, Muscle.

Introduction:

In Indian cuisine fish is used in different manners such as for fish curry, fish biryani, fried fish etc. Fish snacks are the way to prepare value added fish product. Many times, snacks give energy and also protect from overeating. Snack products help to control weight management by reducing the appetite in between meals, at the time meals, and thus preventing overeating (Kirk, 2000). Snacking can be explained as problem-free consumption of easy to handle, small-scale portioned, warm or cold products in solid or liquid form which need limited or no preparation and are deliberate to satisfy the hunger (Kumar et al., 2012; Chudasama et al., 2019). Tilapia is one of the most farmed fish in the world and considered a key aquaculture species. Tilapia production has increased rapidly in the last two

decades. India has set a goal to produce 0.7666 million metric tonnes of Tilapia by 2027. High amount of protein and omega-3-fatty acid is found in fish with low fat, sodium and calories. For fish snacks preparation tilapia fish is selected because it is a exotic species which is well established in Indian water. Total catch of Tilapia from capture and culture fisheries is large. As compared to other fish tilapia shows high protein and omega-3-fatty acid content. This fish snack contains smashed fish meat with combination of mixture of flour. By using Noodles or sachha maker different shapes such as Chakali, sticks, shev, fafada can be prepared. Different flavours can be prepared such as cream and onion, periperi etc. This product shows 18.20% protein per 100 gm. Shelf life of this snack is about 1 month without adding any type of preservatives.

Material and Methods:

From local fish market of Satara freshly caught tilapia fish were taken. All waste parts such as gut, scale, head and caudal fins were removed and cut into pieces. Fish meat then washed with clean water it is boiled in hot water for 15 min. After boiling skin and bones are easy

Flow chart for preparation of fish snacks:

to remove by hand. All boiled meat obtained were smashed finely. 500 ml water boiled and other masala and oil were mixed. In hot water dough is prepared by mixing flour mixture and smashed meat. After preparing proper dough different shapes were prepared by using sachha maker and then deep fried on medium flame.

Proximate Composition: The moisture, crude fat, Crude protein, carbohydrate, crude fibre and ash content of the fish snacks were estimated using hot air oven, Scopus automatic Model, Krelplus automatic Model, Fibraplus automatic model and Muffle furnace, respectively

Sensory Evaluation: Sensory Evaluation were done by experienced panel of judges including

teachers, food experts and postgraduate students of the Department zoology and fisheries Samples were evaluated on basis of the sensory attributes viz. appearance, colour, odour, crispiness, texture and overall acceptability. Feedback analysis of fish snacks was also done

Fig A (Preparation of Fish Snacks): 1: Freshly Cut and Washed Tilapia Fish, 2: Boiled and Smashed tilapia meat, 3: Mixed Flour, 4: Boil Spices and other ingredients in Water, 5: Dough prepared in hot water, 6: Shapes, 7: Fry in oil ,8: Fish Snacks prepared, 9: Packing in jar

Result and Discussion:

Table no. 1: Result of Proximate Analysis

Sr. No.	Test Parameters	Method	Instrument	Results/ UOM (%per 100gm)
1.	Moisture	FSSAI manual of methods of analysis of cereal &cereal product, 2016IS No. 2.0	Hot air oven	12.50
2.	Crude Fat	Basic and Applied biochemistry A Practical Manual 2012IS No.3	Socsplus automatic Model SCS 6E	14.17
3.	Crude Protein	FSSAI manual of methods of analysis of cereal and cereal products 2012 IS, No. 8.8	Krelplus automatic Model:1 KES.06 LE 2. KEL VAC 3 LCASSIC DX KEL PLUS	18.20
4.	Carbohydrates (by cal.)	IS:1656;2007, Milk cereal based complementary foods		41.73
5.	Crude Fiber	Basic &Applied Biochemistry- A Practical Manual 2012-IS No.5	Fibraplus automatic Model- FES6 E	10.10
6.	Ash	Basic &Applied Biochemistry- A Practical Manual 2012-IS, No. 6	Muffle fumace	3.30

Pie chart – Proximate composition of fish snacks

Conclusion:

These various shapes of snacks are made from tilapia fish by incorporating a 30:70 per cent mixture of flour and edible fish muscle. The snacks prepared with a mixture of flour have good sensory attributes. Using of different flours and edible fish muscle studies have shown successful utilisation. This product contains high nutritive values and high protein with minerals. This is an alternative source of protein for everyone and also provides a great source of income. At normal room temperature, they have 30 days shelf life.

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